

Language discourse in curriculum development - comparative perspective from Romania, Poland and Croatia¹²

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Abstract

The article analyzes the language of legislation relating to the core curriculum in 3 countries: Croatia, Poland and Romania, which, freed from socialism, since the 1990s have been building their education systems in an evolutionary way. In particular, the factors of effective teaching are considered. Some other selected aspects of the education system, relevant to the implementation of the curriculum assumptions and contents will also be discussed. The research questions we posed were ‘what language is used in educational legislation for indicators for effective teaching and what is the role of the language?’ For analysis curriculum discourse language was used in comparative perspective. The research indicates the differences in the core curriculum and the language in all three countries. Understanding the context for teaching and understanding the needs of teachers and learners seem to be leading in Croatia. In Romania there is a gap between the language of the official texts and the classroom realities. The need for change of the practical aspects of teaching in the classroom becomes fundamental. While in Poland the language of the curriculum becomes more formal and subordinated to exam requirements, which not so much limits its understanding, but rather stiffens the teaching and learning process.

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Keywords

Curriculum development, national core/school curriculum, school curriculum in comparative perspective, curriculum in school systems, curriculum discourse language in comparative perspective

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Introduction

Curriculum discourse analysis strives to observe a curriculum into its component parts (e.g. learning, teaching, knowledge, society, resources); evaluates how the parts fit together, say in terms of focus and coherence; checks underlying beliefs and assumptions; and seeks justification for curriculum assumptions and choices. Identifying relevant features of the written curriculum language can help reveal potential and actual problems and provide possible solutions, along with recommendations for future support in achieving the previously outlined objectives. Furthermore, comparative analysis coherently identifies biases, perspectives and blindspots with examination of assumptions underlying the curriculum validity and defensibility. It is necessary to take into consideration policy level designs on micro/macro and internal basis in order to gain understanding of program goals, purposes and expected results. Teasing out the assumptions underlying a curriculum is not a straightforward process. Often, we are not aware of the assumptions which influence the curriculum. Uncovering assumptions requires probing beneath the surface of the document, reading between the lines, and making inferences. The curriculum and teaching methods should encourage independent and critical thought, the capacity to question, enquire and reason, to weigh evidence and form judgments, to achieve understanding, and to recognise the provisional and incomplete nature of most human knowledge.

The research question addressed in this study was: what language is used in educational legislation for indicators for effective teaching, such as understanding the context for teaching, understanding the needs of teachers and learners, the quality (careful) planning of courses and materials with the monitoring/evaluation of teaching and learning? Is it a language that explains the intricacies of the education system and acts as a guideline, or is it rather a language of formal requirements? We included a generalized outcome measurement system that can be used to evaluate the effects of mastering subskills on progress towards long-range goals (Fuchs & Deno, 1991). A well-established body of literature supports the effectiveness of one such generalized outcome system referred to as curriculum-based measurement. In curriculum based measurement, the teacher monitors student progress toward long-range goals by using critical indicators of performance (Deno, 1985; Deno & Fuchs, 1987; Fuchs & Deno, 1991; Shinn, 1989). These indicators are reliable and valid with respect to student academic performance and, therefore, are useful for teacher planning and decision-making. The advantage of using critical indicators is that they are easy to use, take little training, and are not specific to a particular curriculum. In addition, they can be used to evaluate whether mastery of selected preskills is helping the student to progress toward the desired long-range goal (Deno, 1985; Deno & Fuchs, 1987; Fuchs & Deno, 1991, 1992; Shinn, 1989).

1. Literature review

Van den Akker (2007) presents his view on curriculum design, starting from the basic concept of what curriculum is, namely an educational trajectory or an educational plan. An educational curriculum is built on various activities, such as policymaking, design and development, evaluation and implementation. The educational curriculum may have various levels, such as the international/comparative (supra level), system/society/nation/state (macro level – which also refers to core objectives and national syllabi), school/institution (meso level), classroom (micro level) and individual/personal (nano level). Van den Akker also explains how each level is represented. The international curriculum is mainly the result of international debates on various educational aims and quality. This has generic content. However, the site-specific curricula are applicable in school environments and at the level of classrooms. Curriculum development can have a specific content, for a narrow application, or general content, designed for long term use, in an ongoing process. It shows the flexible character of curriculum development, that needs to rely on various societal

changes. In order to develop such an educational product, stakeholders and participants are involved, motives and needs are debated with the specific purpose of changing the curriculum in accordance with various parameters, and ideas and efforts are mentioned and integrated into programs that have a practical application. Van den Akker also described the three forms of the curriculum: intended, implemented, and attained. The first is ideal and formal, the second is perceived and operational, while the third is experiential and learned. This classification is important because it relies on what kind of discourse is made manifest in the curricular contents that end up in the implementation phase. It is here where the learning experience of the students is analyzed and the educational outcomes are taken into account.

In Europe there have been developments in the field of education, which focused on implementing educational strategies in European schools, defined as educational establishments controlled jointly by the governments of the Member States of the European Union. These institutions are labeled as public institutions (Office of the Secretary-General of the European Schools). The mission of such schools is to offer multilingual and multicultural education, which presupposes the enactment of a specific kind of curriculum language. The schooling system, for primary education, consists of five years. Primary schools focus on disciplines such as mother tongue, mathematics, the first foreign language, art, music, and physical education. Of particular importance are classes that focus on religion and ethics, and where students from mixed nationalities meet for various activities. It is significant that the focus on happy, healthy, responsible and successful life, the development of abilities and the personality, learning potential support, building the respect for others and the environment, together with others' cultural and social identity and their values, are mentioned only in early education/nursery, not in primary education (Office of the Secretary-General of the European Schools).

The fundamental principle on which the European Schools are built relies on the argument that children discover the world and learn in multiple integrated and interconnected ways. The various ways used by the children to communicate and express themselves seems to be part of what is considered fundamental for their development. From a curricular perspective, the basic tenets of early education curriculum are structured around concepts such as: Me and my body, Me as a person, Me and the others, and Me and the world. This approach favours positive physical, psychological, social, cognitive, and emotional development, doubled by individualised support. Transition into primary education would require meetings, formal and informal, together with information sharing, but teachers should consider the differences between children. Assessment is recommended to be regular and transparent, individualised, helpful, and made in consideration to the child's own self-assessment (Schola Europaea, 2022).

The European Schools can be used as an example of the conceptual basis of curriculum and their practical implementation. However, it should be emphasized that the concept of the school curriculum should refer to universal ideas and priorities adopted in Europe and in the world (e.g. building the European Education Area) and take into account theoretical concepts. Furthermore, in Europe the EU Member States were left responsible for the content of teaching and the organization of the education system, respecting traditions and linguistic diversity.

The issue of educational curriculum presents itself as a challenge between theory and practice, namely, how to develop curricular content, so that students may be able to develop skills, abilities, and competences useful for their life. In 1969, Joseph Schwab presented the issue of curriculum development, in terms of the language used to define its contents. He begins his argumentation by warning that the curriculum strategy needs a new approach, with more effective principles and methods. His second point is that the curriculum needs a new focus on how theory and practice are designed, because either there is too much reliance on theory, or the theory does not lead to the desired outcomes, as presented in the curriculum itself. His third point is that curriculum design needs to focus on the practical aspects. The way he defines the practical aspects is relevant for any age of curriculum design because he refers to a complex discipline, aimed at analyzing choice and action, besides the theoretical aspects, which focus mainly on knowledge. Schwab uses the term "language"

only three times in his article, referring to the perpetual use of old knowledge, but under the guise of new language, which adds nothing to the old meanings, therefore there is no perceivable progress in knowledge (Schwab, 1969).

Schwab's ideas were picked up almost a decade later by Dwayne Huebner (1977), who argues that Schwab presented a thorough evaluation of what the dangers are for the curriculum, namely the incoherence of the curriculum, the failures within schooling, and the disparities within the proper subject field. Huebner also acknowledges the view of B. O. Smith, who argues that concepts such as freedom, openness, activity, self-expression, and creativity, highly theoretical and somewhat unclear and abstract terms, have generated curricular innovation and a wider space for ideological maneuvering, in what Smith calls the ideological and slogan function of curricular discourse. Huebner also agrees that the curriculum development strategies are affected by the lack of curriculum specialists and the experts who should promote national education at a higher political level. Huebner's point is that the issue with curriculum language and discourse is not its theoretical foundation, but that this foundation has little bearing and use in everyday life for the students. In other words, the theoretical aspects of the curriculum have no or little value in the social world. In this context, he mentions that there is a clear-cut separation between the language and the practice in the curriculum design. In this sense, educational practice is disconnected from the “legitimizing and descriptive powers of language”, whereas educational discourse cannot relate to educational practice. Pinar introduced the notion that ‘curriculum’ is a discursive product of a particular era. The curriculum is shaped by political and cultural forces that are dominant at a certain time. This move automatically questions the curriculum understood as a natural artefact. For the ‘Understanding Curriculum’ were used two metaphors: 'text' and 'discourse'. It was much more important for him to understand the curriculum than to develop it. (Pinar, 2006)

Based on the Tyler Rationale (Wraga, 2017), which revolves around four questions that any curriculum development strategy should incorporate, Herbert M. Klieboard presents a decanted version of them in a four-step process: stating objectives, selecting experiences, organizing experiences, and evaluating. Of these, the objectives are most important, since all the other steps depend on how the objectives are formulated. Of special interest are the needs of the learners in connection to their practice and in connection to the objectives. As Klieboard (1970) argues, education is about changing the behavior pattern of students, in order to develop various skills and abilities that would be practical in everyday challenges. Education is not, however, about indoctrination, brainwashing, or sensitivity training, among other things. Students are met where they are in their development, followed by a comparison to a set of prerequisites that would allow the development of a strategy to aid the student to gain as much from the educational process as possible.

On a recent perspective of what curriculum discourse is, Harb (2017) is presenting the view which is at the confluence of curriculum reconceptualization and discourse analysis, meaning that one deals with the need of understanding the curriculum, while the other focuses on language as a socially situated construct, that cannot be neutral. However, the content of the curriculum is expressed and debated in the official educational documents, within the classroom, within educational institutions, and within various social formal or informal gatherings. Such contexts reverberate back to personal teacher-student experiences, where students are encouraged to reflect on their educational experiences and describe them, teachers aid the students in expressing themselves in a genuine manner, and students expand their experiences into a wider collective reflection, with added social explanations.

In essence, curriculum experts design correct theoretical guidance for the practicing teachers, but according to Henderson (1992), this is fantasy, because it is the result of a technocratic impossibility where technically trained experts, would tower over non-experts, by virtue of their specialized training and knowledge, gaining higher positions in politics and various institutions. The issue is that if curriculum studies are reconceptualized to have educational experience as the understanding of scholarly and disciplined understanding, they cannot avoid the theory-practice conundrum. It means that there is a point where experts in curriculum design cannot translate their

educational thoughtfulness to empower others to become educationally thoughtful. Student empowerment occurs when teachers can combine reflective problem solving with dialogical inquiry, in the classroom. Students are encouraged to inquire into issues such as values, problem solving, curriculum leadership, and classroom community leadership. Henderson points out that students can take a deeper path that aims at cooperative learning, complex learning through guided reflective exercises, leading them into the subject of professional empowerment.

Besides the theoretical and practical aspects of curriculum design and discourse, issues such as the health and the wellbeing of students have become educational policy priorities. As Hardley, Gray, and McQuinllan (2021) have argued that decreased mental health and academic outcomes have forced the debate and implementation of the Curriculum for Excellence in Scotland. However, they warn that unclear definitions of wellbeing may become hindrances for implementing a coherent curriculum. If health and wellbeing are reduced to either teaching for achievement, in relation to a predefined learning outcome, or as teaching for a character development, the pedagogic autonomy of teachers will be reduced, thus the curriculum will be affected, specifically because students will be affected first. Frances Christie (1995) tackles the issue of pedagogical discourse in primary school, and connects this specific type of discourse to a set of principles that allows for people to work and function in a way that is valued in a certain culture. The pedagogical discourse is organized around two sets of language choices. The first language choice is based on regulative registers, dealing with goals, purposes, and focus on the teaching-learning activity, while the second language choice deals with the content that is taught and learned. The way these two language choices are bound in the classroom will determine the understanding of what is common knowledge on the part of students, even in primary education.

The curriculum is not limited to the educational environment, but it extends beyond the teacher-student dynamic, into the family. Reinhardt (2018) argues in favour of a curriculum redesign that would allow the power dynamics of teacher-student-family relationships to be built around a flow of information and values. However, the power dynamic will not yield positive results, unless the teacher-student relationship is not reshaped in a more communicative manner. The communication, using adequate language content and structure, works both ways, between teachers and students, and then extending into the family context. If this is so, Manyukhina (2022) argues that there needs to be a children's agency that is put into place, and that agency refers to the ability of an individual to act. The curriculum should facilitate a personal sense of agency, and the structural opportunities to exercise it.

In this study, we sought to apply the concept of generalized curriculum outcome measurement to the evaluation in primary education. More specifically, the study investigated the language discourse of curricula based on validity of selected critical indicators for purposes of identifying effective and ineffective occurrences for monitoring progress toward the long-range goal of competent teaching with the student-centered holistic approach. The research question addressed in this study was: *What language is used in educational legislation for indicators for effective teaching, such as understanding the context for teaching, understanding the needs of teachers and learners, the quality (careful) planning of courses and materials or the monitoring/evaluation of teaching and learning? Is it a language that explains the intricacies of the education system and acts as a guideline, or is it rather a language of formal requirements?*

2. Method

2.1. Procedures

For the purpose of this paper we used desk research methodology which is basically involved in collecting data from existing resources that are known in each country. Desk research is very effective and can be conducted in the starting phase of research as it is quite quick and thural and most of the

basic information could be easily fetched which can be used as a benchmark in the research process. We started with internal desk research that involves internal and existing organizational resources to organize the collected data in such a way that it is not only efficient but also usable. Furthermore, we used external desk research, reaching out from government documents boundaries and collecting relevant information. In order to grasp all necessary data we used online desk research and government published data for the depth of our research process. Research design consists of comparative studies that can be used to increase understanding between cultures and societies and create a foundation for compromise and collaboration. Qualitative, or nonexperimental, is characterized by observation and recording outcomes without manipulation. In comparative research, data are collected primarily by observation, and the goal is to determine similarities and differences that are related to the particular situation or environment of the two or more groups. These similarities and differences are identified through qualitative observation methods. Desk research served as the background to the comparative analysis that was subsequently carried out. It drew on a comprehensive overview of contemporary research in primary education, in particular in relation to the language and competences needed by teachers in order to support specific values written in curricula, EU policy and legislative documents and national documents. It thus provided input to the development of country missions and to the qualitative element of the research.

3. Results

3.1. Romania

The Romanian educational system (Eurydice, 2023) is centrally organized, which means it is administered at a national level by the Ministry of Education, at a central level by collaboration with other ministries, such as the Ministry of Finance, and other institutional structures, in direct subordination to the Ministry of Education. There is also a local level of administration, through each county's School Inspectorate. The Ministry of Education coordinates and organizes all matters of the national educational system, the educational and scientific research, the technological and innovation development, in collaboration with various educational structures. The educational system relies first on the Constitution (chapter 2, art. 32), the Law of National Education, and various laws and Government ordinances.

The educational system is both open and pluralistic. It allows student mobility, by transferring from one school to another, also from one class to another, but also from one field of study to the other. It also provides schooling methods in the official state language, but also in the languages of various national minorities. Since it is considered of national priority, education is multifaceted, organized in both public and private institutions, together with confessional education units. The educational system ensures equal rights to education to all levels and forms, without discrimination. The school buildings are under the administration of the mayor's office.

Public school education is free in Romania and only the diplomas acknowledged by the Romanian state are recognized within it. This means that there is a system of recognizing diplomas emitted by institutions outside Romania. The national education system has 13 grades, which include primary, lower and upper secondary education. The forms of pre-university education are frequency (which is mandatory) and reduced frequency. As for the stages of education, they are creche or nursery (0-3 years), pre-school (3-6 or 7 years), primary education (preparatory grade and grades 1-4), lower secondary (grades 5-8 or gymnasium), upper secondary (grades 9-12/13). At the end of the 8th grade there is a national evaluation examination, which determines the distribution in the upper secondary system. High-school or upper secondary is organized in theoretical, aptitude-based or vocational and technological education. There is also an alternative 3-year professional education, which ends with the certification examination of the professional qualification.

The Romanian Curriculum

In 2020, the Ministry of Education published an important document (Eng. - Fundamental aspects regarding the design, actualization, and assessment of the national curriculum) that focuses on the development, the update and the evaluation of the national curriculum (Palade, 2020). The document is the result of the Europe 2020 Strategy, co-funded through the Human Capital Operational Program 2014-2020. It is a document in full accord with the national strategies for the development of education. The new curricular proposal was elaborated by considering global challenges, the deep changes in Romanian society, and as a renewal of the document emitted in 1998. The new approach considers the curriculum as extending into the continuous development of teachers, school management, educational evaluation, financing the educational system, and elaborating the educational textbooks. The document addresses decision makers within the Ministry Education, curriculum experts and developers, assessment specialists, school inspectors, school principals, teachers, and textbook authors and publishers.

Among other things, the national curriculum supports unitary concepts through all educational stages (pre-primary to high-school, professional, and technical stages), a systemic perspective, an integrated approach, and the creation of an efficient learning environment, which promotes student and teacher wellbeing. Two of the most important elements of the document are the principle of student centered education and the competency centered education. The first aims at learning and its results, which influence the implementation and evaluation of the curriculum, whereas the second aims at organizing the curriculum documents.

The document also takes into account global tendencies, such as globalization, the growing interdependence among states, the technological progress, digitization, demographic challenges, and diversity. At a national level, the document addresses the issue of education for all and for each, life-long education, competency development, decentralization, flexible curriculum, and assessment based on standards. The implemented curriculum should allow students to become autonomous in the learning process, confident in one's abilities, accountable, successful and excellency oriented, and informed, active and proactive.

The fundamental values promoted by the national curriculum are respect for one-self, for others, for diversity, and the environment; accountable for one's own actions in any circumstance; equity oriented; integrity based; innovative and creative; and active citizenship, based on solidarity and participation for the common good. In this context, the educational finalities for primary education revolve around the free, integral, and harmonious development of the child's personality, in full accord with his/her rhythm, and the development of various competencies: literacy, numeracy, multilingualism, science, technology, digital competencies, personal and social skills, and the ability to teach others. These are coupled with civic competencies, entrepreneurial competencies, and cultural sensitivity. At its core, the national curriculum aims at developing knowledge, abilities, and aptitudes.

One of the most used curricular documents is the so-called Program, which describes the identity of a discipline, together with the preparation methods for teaching it. It also offers a framework for classroom teaching, and it is the starting point of lesson planning. It is structured into: General presentation (of the discipline), General competencies, Specific competencies, Learning activities, Learning content, and Methodological suggestions. The general competencies refer to acquisitions made by the students, as they study a certain discipline, whereas, the specific competencies refer to specific stages in student learning acquisitions. For any discipline, there can be between 3 and 6 general competencies, each having 2 to 4 specific competencies.

The language of the curriculum

The language used in most official Romanian educational documents paints a vivid picture of high value goals. The technical terms are in line with European terminology, and the papers reflect the same objectives, that argue for the harmonious and optimistic development of children,

throughout their schooling periods. However, there is a constant criticism that is found throughout online and the published media, and some of the criticism stems from the activity of teachers, claiming that there is disparity, or chasm, between the written documents and the educational process reality. The criticism argues that there is too little practical application in real educational scenarios, despite the optimistic descriptions of competences and educational objectives. One of the latest issues regarding the Romanian educational assessment process describes how the evaluation items at the national exam, in the 8th grade, for Romanian language, were made in accordance with the old version of the curriculum, testing quantity, not competences. The criticism, therefore, aims at showing that the language used in the official documents, has little to no bearing at the classroom level.

3.2. Poland

The curriculum within framework of Polish National Educational System

The system of education in Poland has several levels and consists of preschool education, primary education (starting no later than at 6 years of age, including one year of preparation to school, early school education, i.e. the so-called integrated education (as all the content is basically taught without division into individual subjects) for the first 3 years and the second educational stage - 5 subsequent years) and secondary education (3-5 years). Primary education ends with an external exam, and after passing it, students can continue in a secondary school, i.e. a high school, technical school or a trade school. In Poland, schools are public - financed by the state and from local government funds, and non-public - run by individuals and legal persons (companies and non-governmental organizations). There are also international schools working with students in a foreign language/languages.

The aim of education in primary school is to be the solid foundation of a child's education. The current ordinance states that *"The task of the school is to gently introduce the child to the world of knowledge, prepare them to perform the duties of a student and introduce them to self-development. The school provides safe conditions and a friendly atmosphere for learning, taking into account the individual educational capabilities and needs of the student. The most important goal of education in primary school is to care for the integral biological, cognitive, emotional, social and moral development of the student"* (The Ministry of Education Curriculum Ordinance, 2017).

While the reform of the educational system was being implemented in Poland in 1991, the Minister of National Education introduced an executive act: “The Ordinance on the Core Curriculum of General Education of February 15, 1999” (hereinafter: "Curriculum 1999"), which was the first regulation in Poland after the outburst of political-economic-social changes in 1989 that defined the general goals, tasks and content of education for various educational stages, from primary to high school. This regulation was the core curriculum for general education schools for nearly a decade, before it was replaced by the newer “Ordinance of the Minister of National Education on the Core Curriculum for Pre-school Education and General Education of December 23, 2008” (hereinafter: "Curriculum 2008"). Together with the next reform of education system introduced by the new, conservative government in 2016, “The Ordinance of the Minister of National Education on the Core Curriculum for Pre-school Education and the Core Curriculum for General Education for Primary School of February 14, 2017” (hereinafter: "Curriculum 2017") was introduced. A comparison of all three of the above-mentioned regulations in terms of the effectiveness of teaching and the language used in them (in relation to general requirements) provides information on changes in the education system in Poland over the last quarter of a century.

The "1999 Curriculum" was the shortest (from all three forthcoming regulations of the same topic) and rather more general (than the newer versions of the curricula). Authors of the document focused mostly on defining the goals and content of education for individual educational stages. General indicators of learning outcomes, including students' knowledge, skills and attitudes, were provided. These indicators concerned individual subjects, but also pupils' general skills and attitudes, such as the ability to cooperate or the willingness to cultivate readiness for lifelong learning.

In the “Curriculum 2008” there were used language expressions that suggested higher requirements for schools and teachers than in the previous act relatively more often (such words as "should", "be responsible", "requires" served as indicators). As for the requirements towards school management, the role of the headteacher as the person responsible for the effectiveness of teaching was also articulated with greater strength than before. This 2008 regulation can be summed up as the one which introduced more detailed requirements regarding the content of teaching for particular grades of primary school than the 1999 act. Teaching effectiveness indicators focused e.g. on the level of knowledge, skills and attitudes of students, as well as on the teachers' skills and attitudes and school headteachers.

The language use in the subsequent curricula

The “Curriculum 2017” introduces significant changes compared to the “Curriculum 2008”. Looking at the vocabulary, although phrases such as “duty”, "should", "have to", "need to", "requires" and "responsibility lies with" (and their alterations) are relatively more numerous in the “Curriculum 2008” than in the relatively longer text of the “Curriculum 2017”, wording and expressions actually results consequently in even greater requirements for schools and teachers, than those introduced in 2008. The current law on the core curriculum does not directly define the indicators of effective teaching (as it will be detailed later, these requirements are included in the act "Ordinance on requirements for schools and educational institutions), but contains general and specific objectives for teaching in particular educational areas. On the basis of and in accordance with the above “Curriculum 2017” the following aspects can be monitored and assessed:

- the implementation of educational goals set for specific educational areas,
- students' progress in learning,
- students' knowledge and skills in specific educational areas,
- the development of students' social and emotional skills,
- the degree of students' involvement in the teaching process,
- effectiveness of the methods and forms of the teacher's work,
- effectiveness of individualization of the teaching process in relation to the needs and abilities of students,
- effectiveness of the use of various forms and sources of information and technology in the teaching process.

"Curriculum 2017" introduces not only the above-mentioned aspects but also changes in the content of teaching. Learning performance indicators refer to students' skills and attitudes, such as creative thinking, problem solving, teamwork and digital skills. These indicators also take into account students' individual needs and ensure equality in the face of cultural and linguistic differences.

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In two curricula (from 2008 and 2017) a reader can trace an emphasis on the individualization of the teaching process and even more precise consideration of students' needs and equality in the face of cultural and linguistic differences (than in the curriculum of 1999).

It is difficult to clearly decide whether the language formulations contained in these legal acts mean that schools, headpersons or teachers are now subject to greater or lesser requirements (than before, when the previous document was in force). However, it should be noted that in the 2017 act, adapting the teaching process to the needs of pupils and providing them with the best conditions for development, seems to be particularly important.

Going into detail, compared to the previous regulation (2008), the new regulation (2017) introduced more precise goals and requirements for the observation and support of the child's development in primary school (and earlier, in pre-school), which allows for a more accurate assessment of teaching effectiveness. It should also be added that a more thorough examination of the child's developmental situation may lead to and imply more restrictive (and thus stressful) working conditions for teachers. For the purposes of this article, we analyzed Polish legal acts regarding the core curriculum and curricula, with particular emphasis on the supervision and teaching effectiveness indicators.

Pedagogical supervision has a direct source in the provisions of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland. Article 70(3) of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland explicitly provides for pedagogical supervision over schools and educational institutions, and their detailed regulation has been ordered at the statutory level.

Supervision is exercised by the competent Minister of Education and Science through the superintendent offices operating in voivodeships (regions). It was regulated by the School Education Act of 7 September 1991. The act allowed decentralization of supervision – supervision was to be exercised by the SIO, and at a lower level by directors or managerial staff. Other provisions were general; details were made in the Regulation of the Minister of National Education of 10 December 1991 on the detailed rules for pedagogical supervision.

Supervision was defined precisely in the regulations in 2009. The rules of supervision were indicated therein, in the four forms: evaluation, control, support and monitoring. The inspection of practices used as part of pedagogical supervision carried out before 2009 (Supreme Audit Office, 2002, 2008) indicated a number of shortcomings of the then system:

- unclear division of competences between supervisors;
- the ambiguous role of the inspector, who simultaneously performed three functions at the same time - assessing the quality of schools, checking compliance with legal provisions and dealing with support and guidance for schools;
- excessive focus on controlling school's compliance with legal regulations (instead of improving the quality of education);
- lack of an efficient school support system, e.g. in vocational education. Due to the asymmetric relationship between schools and school inspectors, teacher self-assessment as a quality assurance mechanism has declined in popularity.

Nowadays - in accordance with the Education Law, Art. 55 - pedagogical supervision is used to analyze the process of education and the effectiveness of the work of educational institutions; assessment of the statutory activity of the institution and the conditions; providing support to institutions and teachers. However the legislator emphasized that it should be oriented towards inspiring teachers to apply new solutions at work. The catalogue of goals differs significantly from those indicated in 1991, both in terms of their construction (earlier ones are diagnostic, supportive and informative).

Supervised are mainly documents (qualifications of teachers, implementation of the core curriculum and plans; compliance with the rules regarding assessment, promotion of students to the next grade and conduct of exams, respect for the provisions contained in the statute, compliance with the statute of the school or institution; ensuring safe conditions for students, but also observance of children's rights and dissemination of knowledge about them). In addition, the basis for assessing the situation is the observation and measurement of the effectiveness of the work of the school and other institutions.

Two forms of supervision were indicated in the regulations of 1991: observations and visits. Due to the reform in 2009, the list of forms was expanded in importance. These were: evaluation, monitoring, supporting and controlling. The changes introduced during the last reform led to the reduction of supervision to support and control, the last form being the most extensively described.

Controlling applies to the implementation of statutory objectives, effectiveness, as well as compliance with applicable law, which creates conditions for penalizing practices undertaken in schools. Pre-school and school facilities will not receive support allowing for development resulting from the real needs of children/pupils and local social needs.

The approach puts teachers in the position of an official implementing the regulations. In addition, it strengthens the control activities of curators. Despite the critical perspective presented, it can be assumed that reducing supervision will potentially lead to a reduction in the frequency of supervision and reducing the bureaucratic burden on teachers. The key condition is to limit the provisions on documenting the work of schools and other institutions.

The Ordinance of the Minister of National Education on the requirements for schools and institutions of August 6, 2015 entered into Polish legislation, which after two years was changed into the The Ordinance of the Minister of National Education on the Requirements for Schools and Educational Institutions of August 11, 2017 - these legal acts described separately and in detail the specific requirements that schools and educational institutions should implement. The requirements for schools and institutions are differentiated for levels (separately for pre-school education as well for primary and secondary schools) and types of educational institutions (schools, educational centers, teacher training institutions and others). The analysis of executive acts from 2015-2017 (as amended) allows us to see similarities in some areas required and in the characteristics of the areas. At the same time, the number of the requirements of areas was reduced (from 12 to 9); the division of requirements characteristics into basic and high level was abandoned (currently only general characteristic of requirements is applied); the requirements were simplified and formalized. The analysis of the content of the requirements leads to some conclusions. The introduced changes result in: limitations of the teacher's agency and innovation; slightly strengthening the role of a student in the education process; marginalizing the use of local environmental resources for educational goals; limiting the conditions for improving schools and educational institutions based on innovation.

3.3. Croatia

The Croatian Curriculum

Primary education in Croatia begins with enrollment in the first grade of primary school. It is mandatory for all children, as a rule, it lasts from six to fifteen years of age, and for students with multiple developmental difficulties, it lasts until the age of 21 at the longest. Elementary school lasts eight years and runs regular and special programs. Through primary education, the student acquires knowledge and skills for continuing education (Articles 11 and 12, Law on Education in Primary and Secondary Schools - Official Gazette No.: 87/2008, 86/2009, 92/2010, corr. -105 /2010, 90/2011, 16/2012, 86/2012 - refined text and 94/2013, 152/2014, 7/2017 and 68/2018). For persons older than 15 years who have not completed the legally required primary school, there is the possibility of inclusion in the primary education program for adults. In the primary and secondary education segment, special attention is given to the possibilities for education of students of national minorities in their mother tongue. Primary and lower secondary education is organized as a single structure system and delivered by the network of elementary schools. In the school year 2022./2023. a total of 309 426 (48,48% female and 51,42% male) students were included in the primary education system. The total number of students with developmental disabilities included in primary education amounts to 26 355.

Education in primary and secondary schools is based on the national curriculum, plan, and program. National curricula are adopted for individual levels and types of education in accordance with the framework of the national curriculum document, which determines the elements of the education system for all levels and types of primary and secondary education at the general level. National curricula and the framework are adopted by the minister responsible for education by decision. The curriculum of teaching subjects determines the purpose and goals of learning and

teaching subjects, the structure of an individual subject in the entire educational vertical, the educational outcome and/or contents, the associated elaboration and descriptions of the levels of adoption of the outcome, learning and teaching, and evaluation in an individual teaching subject, together with the list of the necessary qualifications of teachers for the implementation of the curriculum can be determined. The curriculum determines the form of curriculum implementation (compulsory, optional, optional, cross-subject and/or interdisciplinary), the annual number of teaching hours, and their arrangement by class. The curriculum can be common for the level or type at a particular level of education, and exceptionally, it can be adopted along with the curriculum of a specific subject. The minister responsible for education by decision adopts the curriculum of teaching subjects and teaching plans. Pre primary, compulsory primary, and secondary education are provided by public, private, and church educational institutions, public schools, and other educational institutions. The majority of the minority groups in Croatia run their own educational institutions, classes or programmes. Most of these programmes are at preschool level, but a significant number are offered at primary and secondary school level. All of these programmes are approved by MoSES, since they are an integral part of the national school system. At the primary school level three models of minority education are implemented which can be distinguished by: a) the national minority language; b) bilingual teaching; c) nurturing mother tongue and culture (MoSES, 2009a). All children are assessed before they enter primary school. If a child is not deemed to be school ready, entry can be delayed by a year. Assessments are carried out by an expert commission (medical doctor, school psychologist, school pedagogue, classroom teacher) and can be followed by a period of pedagogical observation to determine any special needs the child may have. Parents can appeal the decisions. Education for children with special needs is conducted in regular schools and special schools. Within regular schools, full or partial integration is possible.

The principle underlying Croatian legislation is that integration/inclusion is always best for a child and that only in more severe cases should a student be placed in either partial integration or separate special education classes or schools. Hospital and home teaching are provided by teachers from the nearest primary school. Even special institutions follow the regular programme as much as possible, adapting to the various degrees of disability and offering vocational and employment skills to those who are capable, varying from sheltered workshops to open employment. However, most schools (70%) operate in shifts, and very few schools in Croatia have been adapted to provide wheelchair access. Regulations now require that new school buildings must include access for students with physical disabilities; in some cases, lifts have been installed in existing buildings with the help of community fundraising (OECD, 2007).

Being the main agent of creativity, organization and moderation of the teaching process, a teacher is the cornerstone of the comprehensive education process. The merits of the work of the teachers are rooted in their competencies related to subject knowledge and knowledge of teaching (Alimuddin et. al, 2020, 428; Neopriyeni et. al, 2019, 530). One of the most important documents, affecting each member state of the EU, is Common European Principles for Teacher Competences and Qualifications adopted by the European Commission and which defines the three areas of teachers' competencies. According to this document, teachers should be able to cooperate with others in the sense of being inclusive, encouraging and willing to cooperate; use knowledge, technology and information so that they can transfer different knowledge, use technology effectively and have professional information, i.e. have the skills to prepare students for life as European citizens who think globally (EU, 2005). In its 2003 document entitled *Teacher professional development: an international review of the literature*, UNESCO emphasizes that teacher competencies are those that include: general pedagogical knowledge, professional knowledge, teaching prowess, the skill of connecting theory and practice, the skill of creating a positive learning environment, knowledge and skills of teaching children coming from varying cultural, social and linguistic backgrounds, skills to adapt the teaching process to specific social and political circumstances, knowledge and skills of implementing technology in the teaching and learning process (Villegas-Reimers, 2003). In the Republic of Croatia, scientists have written about teacher competencies and the area of their

implications. The results of a survey conducted in 2005 highlight as teacher competencies - professional knowledge, application of teaching methods in skills, application of information and communication technology in teaching, application of practical skills, methods of monitoring and evaluating students' knowledge, teaching planning, classroom management, communication and cooperation with parents, developing students' self-awareness and self-esteem, encouraging open communication and collaborative relationships among students, working with students with learning difficulties, working with gifted students, encouraging critical thinking and creativity in students, developing independent learning skills, developing ethical reasoning and behaviour in students, readiness for self-evaluation, etc. (Vizek Vidović et al., 2005).

Language impact

When it comes to understanding and determining possible language impacts of teachers in legal context, we must mention the National Curriculum Framework, from 2017. The National Curriculum Framework is a basic educational document of the Republic of Croatia which, *inter alia*, prescribes the goals of educational activities or competencies that children and young people should develop regardless of the type and level of education. This document lists generic competencies grouped in three major sections – forms of thinking (problem solving, decision making, metacognition, critical thinking, creativity and innovation); forms of work and use of tools (communication, cooperation, information literacy, digital literacy and use of technology) and personal and social development (selfmanagement, personal and social development management, connecting with others, active citizenship) (MZO 2017, 15 – 18). In addition, considering this document, one can surmise that there are additional competencies that the teachers need to possess. Thus, for example, it is clear that teachers must be trained to conduct teaching on the topics that span multiple disciplines, which, due to their complexity and since they are novel concepts in the educational system, require special competencies. These are - Entrepreneurship; Learn how to learn; Personal and social development; Information and communication technology (ICT); Health, safety and environmental protection; Civil education. In addition, separate set of legislative documents emphasize the importance of teachers' development of competencies to require for work with children with special educational needs (students with disabilities and gifted students); competencies related to the evaluation of student achievement and competencies that concern process of self-evaluation of educational work (MZO 2017). This is from one point, Croatian written contribution to alignment with EU policies to obtain work on human capital development that offers a solid foundation for the improvement of living conditions, strengthening of democracy and active citizen participation, encouraging respect for human rights and cultural diversity.

4. Discussion

4.1. Romania

Romania has had a troubled post-communism transition period, also in the field of education. Talks of educational reform have always been of great interest in social media. System and systematic changes in education have occurred, especially by re-evaluating and changing the existing National Law of Education (the latest version was put into practice in 2011, with various changes ever since). Being part of the European Union challenged Romanian authorities to be in accordance with European laws and trends. The result was a series of projects and legislative initiatives, that described in positive terms the purpose of education, its outcomes, the assessment process, and the way educational content and teaching methods would allow students to develop skills and competencies, that would allow them to become competent and active citizens, as well as trained professionals in their field of expertise. This is the point where there is a chasm between the language of the official texts and the classroom realities, the failures of the system, and the discrepancy in quality education

between rural and urban schools. Social and mass media have presented the issues that stem from what is written in the official papers and the failures of the system in the classroom. Teachers should have the freedom to choose their educational content and the teaching methods, but are forced to constantly filter the contents for the final national exams, which are not in line with the official documents. Even though the language in the official curriculum is positive, the high percentage of functional illiteracy, especially in rural schools, proves change is needed regarding the practical aspects of classroom teaching, not in the language used in the official educational documents. Despite the orientation towards competence assessment, there is still a high degree of memorization and quantity assessment that does not fall in line with the content of the curriculum. The debate on decentralization has no end in sight.

4.2. Poland

In the last two decades, numerous changes have been made to the curriculum assumptions. Their purpose was to adapt to the requirements of subsequent reforms. It was based on the assumption that the role of the state is to define the curriculum framework. This framework is the point for constructing curriculums for particular subjects of a standardised or more autonomous nature (authorial, innovative and experimental). The Polish curriculum is written in the language of effects relating to three areas of competence: knowledge, skills, social competence. The analysis of changes in legal acts allows us to observe tendencies to expand the content of the curriculum, which is currently the subject of critical dispute. Firstly, it does not bring teachers the opportunity to broaden the issues pursuant to the students' interests and social/technological challenges. Secondly, it discourages teaching staff from creating new curriculums (after 2017, the interest in creating new curriculums decreased - most of them were adapted; and original curriculums). The dynamics of changes in the Polish system makes it difficult to evaluate the curriculum - the curriculum is changed during the education cycle. The evaluation itself needs to be oriented on the effects as well as on an overall and individual value.

Over the last two decades the role of the teacher in shaping students' attitudes and the need to create proper conditions for the implementation of tasks related to education and upbringing provided by the system of education was increasingly emphasised in legal acts. At the same time, with each subsequent legal act in the educational area, school head persons were made more and more responsible for the implementation of tasks resulting from the school curriculum and other legal acts, although this does not happen *expressis verbis*, but is rather concluded from the usage of the language.

4.3. Croatia

It could be said that the importance of a curriculum is realised by the means or structure it provides, to achieve pre-established goals in education. Curricula may be standardised or include a high degree of autonomy - but all share a purpose to meet set aims successfully. The effectiveness of a school curriculum is determined by a wide range of factors and among them are ones for effective teaching: understanding the context for teaching, the needs of teachers and learners, the careful planning of courses and materials and the monitoring of teaching and learning. The Croatian curriculum is competency-based to prepare students for a global context of uncertainty, as part of an overall aim to enable education equity, but this is not fully realised. The national curriculum for primary education is the starting document of compulsory education in the Republic of Croatia, which enables the development of basic competence essential for the realisation of personal potential, continuing education and throughout life learning, which is also the basis of active and responsible participation in society. It is based on developmental educational tendencies in Europe and the world and the Croatian educational tradition in educational documents of the Republic of Croatia. He appreciates the work of all experts who worked on the improvement of the Croatian educational system in recent years and takes over certain good solutions from already started valuable attempts

and initiatives. The Strategy of Education, Science and Technology (2014) is the starting point of the Complete Curriculum reforms, including the creation of the National Curriculum for primary school education. The fundamental principles of the entire curriculum reform are described in the National Curriculum Framework which harmonises the national curricula for all levels of upbringing and education as well as the subject curricula. The national curriculum for primary school education is also harmonised and linked to the Framework for evaluating learning processes and outcomes in primary and secondary schools of the Republic of Croatia, Framework for encouraging and adapting learning experiences and evaluation achievements of children and students with disabilities and the Framework for encouraging learning experiences and evaluation achievements of gifted children and students. It is also harmonised with the National Curriculum for Early Years preschool education and with national curricula for secondary school education and with them it forms a coherent whole. So written language of curricula is formally correct with great emphasis on knowledge of profession and legal EU and country laws. But some of the basic legislative documents do not have a horizontal connections so for eg. within the subject curricula, teachers do not include issues of culture, linguistic diversity, poverty and social justice, society diversity, critical reflection. Future studies should include indicators for holistic based approach within the educational system in order to obtain less hypocritical messages that are beyond informed instructional choices and provide students and teachers with more opportunities to acquire competencies needed for diverse learner needs in the global world.

Conclusion

While there are similarities in the curricula of Romania, Poland and Croatia, each country has unique characteristics that distinguish its approach to education. All three countries have centralized education systems, with a national curriculum and standardized tests. Romanian documents show the national education puts a strong emphasis on vocational education and training in upper secondary education, while in Poland the priority is the development of key competences, and in Croatia the emphasis is on teacher competences, language learning and the inclusion of students with special needs. These differences reflect each country's unique approach to preparing students for a successful professional future, whether entering the labor market directly after completing education or continuing into higher education. A more thorough analysis would require not only a detailed examination of each country's curriculum and other legal acts, but also pedagogy and assessment practices, to name just a few.

In order to create an educational system, which allows for the highest possible number of students to develop knowledge, skills, and abilities, that one might use in everyday life, together with preparing students to become fully functioning citizens, not only of their own countries, but of Europe and the world, the debates between Ministries of Education, educational experts, law and policy makers, curriculum designers, school principals and managers, teachers, and students, needs to be put into accord. How to accomplish such a feat is debatable, but it seems that the biggest and most debated issues are related to the faulty or erroneous manner in which the curriculum content is adapted and put into practice in the classroom, but also whether the assessment process reflects the education content in the curriculum or it is quantity based. The PISA assessment results reflect the status of an educational system, and for Romania, functional illiteracy is found in almost half the student population, most of whom are in the rural schools. Unless there is an honest and consistent process of system evaluation, redesign, and proper implementation, it is the student population that will have most to lose, while emigration from poorer countries towards richer ones will deplete the workforce.

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